

AN IN-DEPTH EXPLORATION OF CONSTRAINTS ENCOUNTERED BY POMEGRANATE FARMERS "

Dr. Pallavi Kolekar¹, Dr. R.V. Chavan² and Dr. Perke³ D.S.¹ Department of Agricultural Economics, Dr. Sharadchnadra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati, Pune, Maharashtra- 413115 India;² Post Graduate Institute, College of Agri-business Management, Chakur, Latur Maharashtra- 413513 India;³ Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, VNMKV, Parbhani Maharashtra- 431402 India.Corresponding Authors email – pallavisudhirdeokate@gmail.com

(MS Received: 23.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:01.01.2024)

MS 3139

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRI-BUSINESS MANAGEMENT)

Abstract:

Encouraging and supporting member-owned producer organizations is essential to providing farmers with the necessary tools for enhancing productivity through efficient, affordable, and sustainable resource use, ultimately leading to higher returns. These organizations can achieve this through coordinated efforts, backed by government support and successful partnerships with the private sector, academia, research organizations, societal groups, and the public sector. A total of 126 sample Pomegranate farmers were chosen for the study. The research needed to include both primary and secondary data in order to comprehend the effectiveness of farmer-producer associations.

Key Words: Constraints, Farmer Producer Organization, Garret's Ranking, Member Farmers,

Introduction

Pomegranate can be grown on diverse types of soils. It is hardy plant and can thrive even under desert conditions. Although, it is highly drought resistant the pomegranate responds well to irrigation. So it is becoming popular in irrigated areas in Maharashtra. The state is having maximum area under pomegranate among all the states in India

The commercial local varieties of pomegranate are Dholka, Alandi, Muskat, Ganesh, Bhagwa, Mrudula and Arakta. The flesh of Dholka is pinkish white, seeds are soft but juice is more acidic, muskat has slight pinkish flesh, soft seeds and good sized fruits. The flesh of Bhagwa is red and seeds are also red. This variety popular in sangola in solapur district. Cheema (1954) evolved a superior variety namely Ganesh (GBG.1) by method of seedling selection selection from the seedling selection from the seedling raised from the seed of Alandi variety .Ganesh variety possesses pink, flesh, soft seeds and sweet agreeable taste by the cultivators in Maharashtra and popular in Solapur, Satara, Buldhana and Pune district.

Materials and Methods:

The Western Maharashtra region was specifically chosen for the study. Pune, Sangli, Satara, and Solapur districts in Western Maharashtra were specifically chosen for the study because they have larger areas dedicated to pomegranate cultivation. Pomegranate was the main crop grown by this area, hence it was chosen for the study. Due to similar climatic circumstances, 18 Pomegranate farmers were chosen from the same area. A total of 126 sample farmers were chosen for the study. The research needed to include both primary and secondary data in order to comprehend the effectiveness of farmer-producer associations.

Analytical Tools:

Using Garret's ranking technique, restrictions faced by both Pomegranate farmers were analyzed. The Garrett's table, the percent positions were converted into scores. Thus for each factor, the scores of the various respondents were added and then mean values were

estimated. The attributes with the highest value was considered as the most important one and the other followed in order.

Percent Position = $100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$

Where,

R_{ij} stands for rank given for the i th factor ($i=1,2,...10$) by the j th individual ($j=1,2,...40$)

N_j stands for several factors ranked by j th individual.

Results and Discussion:

Constraints are limitations, restrictions, or factors that impede or restrict the ability to accomplish a task, achieve a goal, or perform a particular action. Identifying and understanding these constraints is crucial for developing strategies, policies, and interventions to support farmers and improve agricultural productivity. So attempt had been made to identify constraints and ranked by Garret's ranking technique.

Constraints faced by Pomegranate farmer

The constraints faced by Pomegranate farmers of in production of pomegranate were depicted in table 2. The production constraints faced by pomegranate farmers are presented in rank according to Garrett's ranking technique. There are ten major constraints in pomegranate cultivation of Pomegranate farmers as stated by the sample farmers. The results from the table reveals that oily Spot attack difficult to control was the major problem faced by sample farmers is ranked first with Garrett's score 56.30. It is found to be a major constraint in the study area. The second major problem faced by sample farmer was Uncertainty of prices and their Garrett's score is 54.40. Lack of technical knowledge was the another major constraints faced with 52.19 Garrett,s score. Oily spot attacks on crops, been ranked first, represented a significant concern for Pomegranate farmers. This disease issue could have led to substantial crop losses and reduced yields. Integrated pest management and disease control strategies were critical to address this top-ranked constraint.

Table 2: Garrett's Ranking For Constraints Perceived By Pomegranate Farmers

Sr. No.	Constraint	Total Garrett Score	Mean Score	Rank
1	High cost of fertilizers and other inputs	6488	51.49	IV
2	Lack of quality storage facility	5839	46.34	VIII
3	Lack of technical knowledge	6576	52.19	III
4	Oily Spot attack difficult to control	7094	56.30	I
5	Uncertainty of prices	6855	54.40	II
6	Labour problems	6459	51.26	V
7	Intercultural operations are more expensive	5595	44.40	X
8	Difficulty to getting branded insecticide and pesticides	5968	47.37	VI

9	Load shading in electric supply	5841	46.36	VII
10	High Transportation costs	5781	45.88	IX

Pomegranate farmers were worried about the volatility and uncertainty in agricultural product prices. Price fluctuations could have been affected their income and financial planning. Strategies might be included market diversification, price hedging, or establishing market linkages to mitigate price uncertainty. Pomegranate farmers recognized the importance of technical knowledge in modern agriculture. Lack of access to information and expertise might be hindered their ability to optimize their farming practices. Efforts to provide training, extension services, and knowledge-sharing platforms could have been empowered non-members with necessary skills.

The cost of pricey supplies and fertilizers worried Pomegranate farmers since it may have a big impact on their production costs. Reduced profitability and economic viability for non-members may have resulted from high input costs. One way to have overcome this limitation would have been to encourage economical farming methods or to subsidize inputs.

Farmers who were not members of FPO acknowledged that labour related issues arose in their farming operations. The timely completion of duties and productivity may be impacted by these issues. This limitation may have been overcome through mechanization and labor-use efficiency training initiatives. It was difficult for non-members to obtain reputable, branded insecticides and pesticides. Crop protection and productivity could be impacted by this restriction. Increasing the availability and distribution of high-quality agrochemicals could be one of the strategies.

Farming operations might have been hampered by load shedding-related interruptions in the electrical supply. Several farming processes, including as irrigation and post-harvest processing, required consistent electricity. It might have been necessary to use alternate energy sources or increase grid stability to get around this restriction.

Reduced product quality and post-harvest losses could have been the outcome of inadequate storage facilities. It's possible that non-members had trouble keeping their farm products preserved, which affected how marketable they were. This restriction might have been lessened by making investments in better storage infrastructure or encouraging better storage practices.

Excessive transportation expenses may have decreased farmers' profit margins and increased overall output costs. Pomegranate farmers were worried about how much it would cost to get their farm goods to markets. Developing the infrastructure, cutting the cost of logistics, and enhancing market access were possible strategies. Concerns over the high expenses of intercultural farming enterprises were voiced by non-members. Investigating affordable cross-cultural practices and technological uptake might have been one way to get around this restriction. Similar study were conducted by Jadhav *et al.*, (2019), Rede *et al.*, (2018) and Thombre *et al.*, (2020).

Conclusion:

Interpreting these rankings helps in reflecting on the challenges that Pomegranate farmers faced and the potential strategies that could have been implemented to address these constraints. Policymakers, agricultural organizations, and Pomegranate farmers were all made aware of these barriers and potential solutions to collaborate on improving the productivity and resilience of the agricultural sector. The results underscored the significance of customized interventions and assistance in mitigating these limitations, ultimately resulting in enhanced means of subsistence for Pomegranate farmers.

Recommendation:

To offer certificate programs, training courses, etc. NIAM, BIRD, NIFTEM, MANAGE, and VAMNICOM are among the organizations holding the Sectors Skill Counseling Certificate, along

with centers for entrepreneurship education and colleges catering to the agricultural sector.

Legal reform must be implemented to establish a business-friendly atmosphere that enables farmers' collectives to transact in contemporary, export-focused marketplaces.

References:

1. **Bhavani,G., Sreenivasulu, M. and Naik, R. V. 2021.** Constraint Analysis of Quality Seed Production in Telangana using Garrett's Ranking Technique. *Journal of Community Mobilization and Sustainable Development*. 16(2):560-564.
2. **Chopade, S.L., Kapse, P.S. and Dhulgand, V.G. 2019.** Constraints Faced by the Members of Farmer Producer Company. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 8(08):2358-2361. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2019.808.273>
3. **Debahash Buragohain and Dubey, J.P. 2021.** Contract Farming: A Constraint Study using Garrett Ranking Technique. *Indian Journal of Extension Education* 57(2):212-215. DOI: 10.5958/2454-552X.2021.00055.
4. **Goyal, Nitin and Goyal, S.K. 2022 .** Major Constraints in Production and Marketing of Onion in Haryana. *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education* 22(2):38-43.
5. **Mohanty Suchitra, Mandal Subhasis and Rahim K.M.B. 2015.** Economics of Hill Farming System with special Reference to Feasibility and Constraints in Production of Organic Commodities in Meghalaya India. *International Conference*.9-11. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279940840>
6. **Mukesh Kumar and Rakesh Singh. 2020.** Identify the Constraints of Farmer Producer Organisation in SwaiMadhopur District of Rajasthan. *Ind. J. Pure App. Biosci.* 8(3):296-299. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18782/2582-2845.8123>
7. **Nisha Devi, Krishan Kumar Raina and Ravinder Sharma. 2020.** Constraints Perceived by the Farmers of Himachal Pradesh in Organic Farming. *Economic Affairs*. 65(2):213-218. DOI: 10.46852/0424-2513.2.2020.12
8. **Patel, R.R., Patel, P.K., Patel, R.M. and Patel, K.J. 2018.** Major constraints faced by farmers of Sabarkantha district in Gujarat. *Internat. Res. J. Agric. Eco. & Stat.*9(1):133-136. DOI :10.15740/HAS/IRJAES/9.1/133-136.
9. **Pawariya V., Poonia M. K., Ram N., Yadav M. M., Dagar V.2020.** An analysis of constraint and problems in production and marketing of Nagauri (Paan) methi in Rajasthan State of India. *Environment Conservation Journal*, 21(3):171-176.
10. **Ramesh Madhav Jadhav1 , Dr. Amit Kumar Mishra2 ,2023** "Constraints Faced By Pomegranate Growers Of Maharashtra In Adoption Of Recommendedcultivation Practices".Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxvi, April, Multilogic In Science, Issn 2277-7601, Page 653-654.
11. **Rede G.D, Janee Yumlembam, Sorokhaibam Somina Devi and K. Bhattacharyya. 2018.** Garrett's Ranking Analysis For Constraints Faced in Production and Export of Pomegranate. VOL. VIII, ISSUE XXV, April 2018 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601. 8(25):192-193.
12. **Rede, G. D. and K. Bhattacharyya. 2018.** Marketing and Constraints Analysis of Pomegranate in Solapur District of Maharashtra. *Economic Affairs*. 63(1): 99-106.
13. **R. R. Jadhav1 , S. G. Puri2* and V. B. Dhakne3 2023** "Constraints Faced And Suggestions Made By The Pomegranate Cultivators In Adoption Ofimproved

- Pomegranate Cultivation Practices" Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxxvi, April, Multilogic In Science, Issn 2277-7601, Page 626-628.
14. **Sahoo Ashok Kumar, Srinibash Dash and Sudhanshu Sekhar Rath. 2020.**The Application of Garrett Scoring Techniques for Assessment of the Farmer Problems in Obtaining and Repayment of Agricultural Credit. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. 9(03):5192-5199.
 15. **Shanjevika, V., Balasubramaniam, P., Venkatesa, N., Palanichamy, J., Venkata Pirabu and Duraisamy, M. R. 2022.**Evaluation of Constraints Encountered by Banana Growers in Adopting Water Management Practices using Henry Garrett Ranking Technique. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*. 12(11):1965-1971.
 16. **Sharma, M., Suryavanshi P. and Singh, Y.2020.** Garrett's ranking analysis of constraints influencing off season vegetable growers in District Mohali. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. Sp9 (2): 46-49.
 17. **S.M. Hade*, R.V. Nainwad, S.R. Kalam and S.E. Tistak, 2018** "Studies On Effect Of Different Polywrappers On Success Of Air Layering In Pomegranate (Punica Granatum L.) Cv. Bhagwa" Vol. Viii, Special Issue (D) August 2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Page 190-192.
 18. **Thombre, R. F., Deshmukh, K. V., More, S. S. and Chavan, R. V. 2020.**Constraint and Suggestion Analysis in Production and Marketing of Maize in Marathwada Region of Maharashtra using Garrett's Ranking Technique. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 9(8):1773-1778.
 19. **Verma, A.K., Singh, V.K., Asha, K., Dubey, S.K. and Verma, A.P. 2021.** Constraints Perceived by the Members and Non-members towards Functioning of FPO-AKPCL in Kannauj District of Uttar Pradesh. *Economic Affairs*. 66(2):335-341.
 20. **W. Ao and B.K. Jamir. 2020.** Application of garret ranking technique in studying the problems of bamboo cultivation: A case study of Mokokchung district, Nagaland. *Indian Journal of Hill Farming*. 33(2):311-315.